

I-CISK
HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

**Deliverable D5.4 - I-CISK Platform Final Technical
Specification and Platform Manual**

Sep, 2025

Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge

This document builds upon Deliverables D5.1, D5.2 and D5.3. It presents final technical specifications where different from what has been presented earlier, i.e., in D5.3. This deliverable also provides the complete user manuals for the I-CISK climate service platform, which is developed within the I-CISK project. Furthermore, the Auto-CS composer is presented and discussed.

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Executive Summary

The I-CISK project, "Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge," develops web-based climate services by combining scientific and local knowledge, iteratively incorporating user feedback. Deliverable D5.4 documents the final release of the I-CISK Climate Service Platform, providing user manuals and technical summaries for each Living Lab (LL), highlighting their use cases. It also introduces the innovative Climate Service AUTO Composer, an LLM-based interface enabling users and providers to customize and deploy new climate service applications. This document builds on D5.2 and D5.3.

The seven LL focus, by design of the project, on very different use cases and applications; hence each user manual also differs accordingly.

- In the living lab in **Andalucia, Spain** six Climate Services have been co-developed for agriculture, offering tools for historical analysis, future projections, and hydrological information. These services provide farmers with critical data on temperature, precipitation, drought, and agricultural indicators to support planning and mitigation measures.
- The I-ISK platform offers for the Living Labs in **Emilia Romagna, Italy** and **Alazani River basin, Georgia** preoperational daily discharge forecasts for selected river sections with historical context and management thresholds, targeting water managers and technicians. Users can access daily discharge views, medium-range summaries, and seasonal cumulative-volume views, supporting decisions like withdrawal management and enabling data export for reporting.
- The Climate Service of the Living lab in **Rijnland, Netherlands**, provides specialized climate information for recreational boating, agriculture, water management, and tree nurseries. Users can quickly assess drought, precipitation deficits, water inflow, and future climate scenarios for adaptation..
- The Living Lab of **Crete, Greece** provides a web-based platform with four key services offering forecasts and data at various temporal and spatial scales supporting decision-making in tourism, water management, and long-term climate adaptation for the island of Crete.
- The **Budapest** Living Lab's CityZcan platform offers urban heat island management in Hungary. It aids tourism, healthcare, and urban planning with thermal monitoring and early heatwave warnings through interactive web maps, an open-source thermal image analysis plugin, and an open-format data archive.
- The **Lesotho** Climate Service provides seasonal drought information through two deployments: a public I-CISK portal for exploration and an operational IBF platform used by the Lesotho Red Cross for day-to-day operations. Both systems utilize the Precipitation Drought Index (PDI) to assess drought likelihood and severity, with the IBF portal additionally quantifying drought risk and exposed populations to support anticipatory action.

A central motivation behind the development of the Climate Services is to lower the entry barriers for non-specialist users, who often lack advanced programming skills, by giving them direct and user-friendly access to upstream data services (e.g., Copernicus CDS, GEOSS). By making climate data readily available, the Climate Service empowers users to configure tailored applications that reflect their specific contexts and decision-making needs.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	3
List of Figures	5
List of Tables	8
1. Introduction	9
2. Methodology	10
3. General Technical Platform Overview	11
3.1 Technical specifications of the I-CISK platform – Final Release	11
3.2 Common Components	11
3.3. Installation Overview	13
4. I-CISK Climate Service Manual and Tutorial	14
4.1. Andalucía Living Lab (Spain, LL1)	14
4.2. Emilia Romagna Living Lab (Italy, LL2)	22
4.3. Rijnland Living Lab (Netherlands, LL3)	27
4.4. Crete Island Living Lab (Greece, LL4)	31
4.5. Budapest Living Lab (Hungary, LL5)	44
4.6. Alazani River basin Living Lab (Georgia, LL6)	50
4.7. Lesotho Living Lab (LL7)	57
5. Climate Service LLM-based AUTO Generator	61
5.1 Introduction and Purposes	61
5.2 Technical Manual	62
5.3 User Manual	72
6. Summary	81
7. Challenges and Solutions	82
8. Conclusion and Future Work	83
9. Appendices	84
9.1 Acronyms	84

List of Figures

Figure	Caption (shortened)	Page
Figure 4.1-1	Screenshot of the landing page of the Spanish LL showing the six CS as tiles and as tabs in the navigation bar at the top of the website..	14
Figure 4.1-2	Screenshot of the CS “Mapas previsión a 6 meses”.	15
Figure 4.1-3	Screenshot of the CS “Mapas climáticos históricos”.	16
Figure 4.1-4	Screenshot of the CS “Estaciones climáticas históricas”.	17
Figure 4.1-5	Screenshot of the CS “Proyecciones climáticas”.	18
Figure 4.1-6	Screenshot of the CS “Indicadores agroclimáticos”.	19
Figure 4.1-7	Screenshot of the CS “Información hidrológica”.	20
Figure 4.2-1	GUI landing page with station list (top and bottom zoom left), station position on the map (center and bottom zoom) and dashboard to activate specific graphs with access to station data and the forecasts available (top right).	22
Figure 4.2-2	Forecast discharges selectable through the GUI;	23
Figure 4.2-3	Average forecast volumes in the coming season, provided versus historical average in the same period obtained from the last 10 years of observation, includes statistical variability in boxplot fashion.	24
Figure 4.2-4	The daily forecast accessed by the user for the selected station compared to the relevant thresholds.	25
Figure 4.2-5	Toggling on uncertainty of the probabilistic forecast to get confidence level.	26
Figure 4.3-1	Left: Landing page for the CS for the selected role of “Waterbeheer”. Right: Summary calendar week view of the drought situation in the Rijnland region.	27
Figure 4.3-2	Combined map and time series representation of the precipitation deficit.	28
Figure 4.3-3	Screenshot of the CS “Afvoer Lobith” showing the runoff of the river Rhine near Lobith.	29
Figure 4.4-1	Initial screen of the Living Lab of Crete developed in I-CISK.	31
Figure 4.4-2	Initial screen of Seasonal Indicators service.	32
Figure 4.4-3	Selection of seasonal indicator and map interactions.	34

Figure	Caption (shortened)	Page
Figure 4.4-4	Graph of the temporal variation of the selected indicator (Frequency of North Winds > 7BF) for the next 7 months.	35
Figure 4.4-5	Initial screen of Hydrological Indicators service.	36
Figure 4.4-6	The forecasts of river discharge are presented as time series (aggregated at 15-days intervals) for the forecasting horizon of 7 months, along with their statistical properties.	37
Figure 4.4-7	Individual members and statistical properties of the hydrological ensemble.	37
Figure 4.4-8	Initial screen of the Water Management Service for OAK end user.	38
Figure 4.4-9	Customized views of the Water Management Service for OAK.	49
Figure 4.4-10	Initial screen of the Climate Projections service.	40
Figure 4.4-11	Steps for selecting an indicator and displaying the climate projections map.	41
Figure 4.4-12	Toggler for displaying map values as absolute or relative.	42
Figure 4.5-1	Screenshot of the landing page of the CityZcan Webpage.	45
Figure 4.5-2	Examples of two map layers for the Terézváros district in Budapest under study.	46
Figure 4.6-1	Screenshots of the GUI landing page with station list (top left), station position on the map (top and bottom left as zoom in) and dashboard to activate specific graphs with access to station data and the forecasts available (top right and bottom right as zoom in).	51
Figure 4.6-2	Screenshots of the hydro forecast component _ average monthly graph.	52
Figure 4.6-3	SPI-3 index.	53
Figure 4.6-4	Temperature & Precipitation module.	54
Figure 4.7-1	Main service landing page for Lesotho – public demo version.	58
Figure 4.7-2	Impact-Based Forecasting (IBF) Portal overview.	59
Figure 4.7-3	Impact-Based Forecasting Portal Warning state example (“Drought ongoing”).	60
Figure 5.2-1	Component diagram of the auto composer structure.	63
Figure 5.2-2	Sketch of the auto composer functional subgraphs.	65
Figure 5.2-3	Auto composer User responses interpretation.	69
Figure 5.3-1	Screenshot of the Auto composer control panel layout.	73

Figure	Caption (shortened)	Page
Figure 5.3-2	Auto composer Generation of code example.	73
Figure 5.3-3	Auto composer input confirmation example.	75
Figure 5.3-4	Auto composer output confirmation example	76
Figure 5.3-5	Auto composer Quick Actions section	77
Figure 5.3-6	Auto composer File Manager section	78
Figure 5.3-7	Auto composer Preview Notebook section	78
Figure 5.3-8	Auto composer access to technical documentation	79

List of Tables

Table	Caption (shortened))	Page
Table 3.2-1:	Tabular summary of the components of the climate data ingestor based on the detailed descriptions in D5.3.	12

1. Introduction

The I-CISK project, "Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge," aims to develop innovative climate services by integrating scientific and local knowledge to address the specific needs of various regions.

This deliverable, D5.4, targets users of the developed Climate Services (CS) with some preliminary knowledge about climate service technologies. Technical summaries are kept at a high level avoiding as much as possible technical language and specialised IT terminology.

The I-CISK project is built on a foundation of co-design, involving stakeholders from the early stage, so that the climate services developed are not only scientifically robust but also tailored to the specific needs of local user communities. The project employs a collaborative approach where requirements are gathered, discussed, and verified among stakeholders and work packages through the establishment of "Climate Service Task Forces" (CSTFs). These CSTFs are instrumental in defining and refining climate services for each Living Lab, ensuring that solutions meet local needs and are supported by robust data integration and processing frameworks.

The I-CISK platform described hereafter is a cloud-based system utilising advanced technologies such as Docker and Kubernetes for scalability and flexibility. It supports the ingestion, processing, and visualisation of climate data from multiple sources, seeking high performance and reliability. The platform's architecture has evolved to incorporate best-of-breed open-source components, enhancing its functionality and effectiveness.

Each Living Lab within the I-CISK project has developed tailored solutions for climate data integration, back-end processing, and front-end visualisation. This deliverable details the usage of the front-end components in I-CISK's LLs in Spain, Emilia Romagna, Rijnland, Crete, Budapest, Georgia, and Lesotho as developed by the end of the project. Beyond the specifically co-designed CS for each LL, a CS Auto-composer (Task 5.4) has been developed (see [Section 5](#)). It is based on LLM agents interacting with the user through chat prompts to integrate and visualise climate relevant data in a jupyter notebook.

After the initial testing phase, as detailed in the previous iteration of development, work has focused on ensuring quality goals through rigorous functionality, performance, and usability testing. User feedback received during several iterations of implementation has been instrumental in refining the platform, leading to improvements in navigation, data visualisation, and overall user experience.

2. Methodology

The CS platform has jointly been developed as an open-source solution. The source code is hosted at GitHub and is available within the GitHub organisation “I-CISK”: <https://github.com/icisk>.

Note: The methodology has not changed since D5.2 and is repeated for improved readability.

Following the overall I-CISK project principle of co-design, the requirements of each Living Lab (LL) have been gathered, discussed and verified as a collaborative effort among several work packages (see D5.2,). The requirements have been collected as user stories (see Table 1). The user stories formulated by the LL leads and their stakeholders focus i.e. on the visualisation of local information products derived from large scale Climate Services, such as those developed by the Copernicus program. The analytical requirements to derive the essential information have only been implicitly contained in the user stories and needed to be further detailed by the corresponding domain experts in the I-CISK project.

In order to achieve an intense co-development of the actual solutions for each Living Lab based on the collected user stories, so called “Climate Service Task Forces” (CSTF) had been established in the I-CISK project. These CSTF define the day-to-day steering group for each LL and contain one representative of the LL and one from each WP. While this group is intentionally small, the representatives in each CSTF can of course build upon the team and work done in the WP they represent. Depending on the individual set-up and phase within the co-design process of each LL, the CSTFs met with different and varying intensities.

Each CSTF constitutes an agile development team where the LL representative acts as the “product owner” and takes responsibility that the CS under development suits the needs of the stakeholders of the LL. In an iterative process, first mock-ups (plain sketches or rudimentary functional components) have been presented and refined during discussions with LL leads, but also with stakeholders where appropriate. Discussions and decisions taken on the mock-ups informed the development of first prototypes for each LL, which have been presented and discussed first with the LL lead, as well with stakeholders. In this early stage of the prototype development, where different options are assessed and the vision of the CS, i.e. its user interface, still needs to converge within the CSTF, individual solutions building on related work of the involved partners had been developed. In order not to hinder these vibrant developments, the back-end components managing the data access have also been individually dealt with in each of the LL prototypes, often relying on only snapshots of data. In the recent phase of the co-development, the CSTF have decided upon the CS design and the prototypes have been harmonised, e.g. building upon the central CS data infrastructure of the I-CISK CS platform and also by re-using available front-end components among several LLs.

3. General Technical Platform Overview

3.1 Technical specifications of the I-CISK platform – Final Release

The developments are grounded in the architecture design that has been developed from the start of the I-CISK project and that was initially outlined in Deliverable D5.1 and further detailed in D5.2. Throughout the close cooperation with the Living Labs within the co-design of the separate Climate Services, the architecture of the I-CISK Climate Service Platform has been continuously refined to the actual final release that has already been documented in D5.3 and did not receive any technical architectural updates since then.

3.2 Common Components

Note: The components have not changed since D5.3 and this section is merely a brief summary of corresponding sections in D5.2 and D 5.3 for improved readability.

Cloud Computing - Telecom Cloud

The CS platform is deployed and operated in the Open Telekom Cloud (OTC), a European provider and contributor to the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem. Services for the living labs, including the landing page, are organized within a dedicated namespace in a Kubernetes cluster at the OTC, sharing common infrastructure components like cert-manager and a nginx ingress controller. Each component (living lab app or landing page) has its own workload, service, ingress, and optional persistent volume claims.

Climate Data Ingestor Docker

The Climate Ingestor Docker is a crucial component of the I-CISK project's cloud-based Climate Service (CS) platform. Its primary function is to handle the ingestion of various types of climate data from multiple sources, ensuring that the data is accurately fetched, processed, and stored for further analysis and visualisation. The Climate Data Ingestor infrastructure is based on Pygeoapi, making the component consistent and OGC compliant.

The previous deliverable D5.3 contains a detailed list of resources integrated into the climate data ingestor providing a brief description, type, data source, API or link. The datasets include temperature, precipitation, river discharge, and drought forecasts, sourced from entities like AEMET, CDS, CREAM, and SMHI, and are used across Spain, Italy, Georgia, Lesotho, and the Netherlands.

For each data source, one or more ingestion processes are defined as Pygeoapi processes. These processes can be executed manually via a REST API call or automatically through scheduled invocations, configured by editing a scheduler file that specifies the dataset, query, and frequency. The scheduler is composed of cron jobs hosted on Kubernetes within the OTC.

Upon completion, each ingestion process creates a ZARR file storage in a cloud bucket for raster data, or a GeoJSON file for vector data, and updates the Pygeoapi configuration with a new collection referencing the file path. For improved performance and data persistence, ZARR files can also be stored directly within the Pygeoapi instance if a volume is configured. Once a new collection is generated, its data can be directly queried via OGC API. A summary of the components of the climate data ingestor is presented in [Table 3.2-1](#).

Table 3.2-1: Tabular summary of the components of the climate data ingestor based on the detailed descriptions in D5.3.

Component	Function	Features
Scheduler	Triggers fetching of new data at regular intervals to update the platform with the latest available data.	Configurable data fetching frequencies (hourly, daily, weekly); supports multiple schedules for different data sources.
Data Fetcher	Connects to external data sources and retrieves required data, handling different data formats and ensuring seamless transfer.	Supports continuous data ingestion from various sources (Copernicus, ECMWF, SMHI, local weather stations); manages connections and data fetching protocols (API requests, FTP downloads).
Data Processor	Transforms raw data into a standardized format for storage and analysis, performing data cleaning, conversion, and aggregation.	Converts data into cloud-optimized formats (ZARR) for raster data; ensures compatibility with platform's data storage and retrieval systems; handles time-series, spatial (raster and vector), and textual data.
Individual Ingestors for Data Sources and Living Labs (LLs)	Specialized ingestors tailored to specific data sources and Living Labs, configured to handle unique requirements and data formats.	Customized setup for continuous data ingestion from specific sources; dedicated ingestors for setting up and managing individual data for each LL, ensuring tailored data processing and storage.
General Climate Data Downscaling	Downscaling and bias correction of forecasted data.	Downscaling and bias correction of forecasted data based on historical time series data encapsulated as a dedicated process.

Common Landing Page Web Docker

The landing page¹ uses a common web server landing page container image based on the nginx:latest image with a few additional files for styling and templating. These include bootstrap css, font and javascript files. See Deliverable D5.3 for more details

3.3. Installation Overview

The I-CISK CS platform is based on a Kubernetes (k8s) set-up. It contains two instances of pygeoapi, one database and several containers for each LL's frontend application. In addition to that, cloud storage is needed. One instance of pygeoapi is used to ingest new data and process it, the second is used to serve the data. The whole service, including the k8s-cronjobs to ingest the data, is coordinated by k8s-manifests. To connect all entities it is crucial to manage all env variables to pass passwords, access tokens and such. To do that one needs to set github-actions secrets that are used during the build as well as k8s secrets.

¹Available at: <https://i-cisk.dev.52north.org/>

4. I-CISK Climate Service Manual and Tutorial

Each Living Lab includes a user manual and technical overview, detailing how to effectively use the climate services. These resources guide stakeholders through the functionalities of the front-end interfaces, data visualisation tools, ensuring they can fully reveal the provided information for decision-making.

Because each Living Lab has distinct objectives, users, datasets, and deployment choices, the user-manual descriptions below are tailored to each lab and may therefore differ in length and structure. Each section prioritises the lab's specific interface, data, and workflows; where helpful we include a concise summary or an illustrative use case, otherwise we focus on the technical description needed for effective use.

4.1. Andalucía Living Lab (Spain, LL1)

User Manual

The landing page of the Spanish living lab ([Figure 4.1-1](#)) depicts screenshots from the different CS that have been co-developed for users mainly from the agricultural sector. The top shows the navigation bar repeating all six CS. The navigation bar is retained for all CS views and allows users to quickly and easily navigate between the CS.

Figure 4.1-1: Screenshot of the landing page of the Spanish LL showing the six CS as tiles and as tabs in the navigation bar at the top of the website.

Figure 4.1-2: Screenshot of the CS “Mapas previsión a 6 meses” here depicting the uncertainties associated with the disaggregation process.

The CS “Mapas previsión a 6 meses” (Figure 4.1-2) depicts the downscaled, bias corrected and disaggregated forecasts for the coming six months. The variables presented are monthly temperature and precipitation based on ensemble forecasts obtained from the CDS. The first two drop down selectors allow the user to select the issue date of the forecast (here August 2025) along with the forecast horizon (3 months = November 2025). The third dropdown menu selects the variable to be presented while the toggle switch lets the user move between phenomenon and uncertainty associated with the disaggregation process. By clicking into the map, the development of the selected pixel over time is shown as a time series plot below the map. Additionally to the median value shown in the map, further percentiles are plotted along in the time series view. **This CS allows the user to assess the heat stress and expected precipitation for the farm land to plan for mitigation measures ahead of time.**

Figure 4.1-3: Screenshot of the CS “Mapas climáticos históricos” showing interpolated monthly mean temperature observations for April 2000 on the left half of the map and for April 2015 on the right half of the map. Clicking into the map (red circle) opens time series plots below the map window.

The second CS is titled “Mapas climáticos históricos” allows to compare monthly interpolated observations of temperature, precipitation and a set of drought indices since the year 2000. Shown in [Figure 4.1-3](#) are the interpolated monthly mean temperature observations for April 2000 on the left half of the map and for April 2015 on the right half of the map. The slider below the map allows to move the break between the left and right side selection in East and West direction. The dropdown menus above the map control the selection of the variables shown in the map. Selecting drought indices adds another dropdown menu to select among SPI (Standardized Precipitation Index) and SPEI (Standardized Precipitation Evatransporation Index) for different temporal horizons from 3 to 24 months. As different temporal horizons are used for different decisions. Clicking into the map (location depicted as red circle) opens a time series view, where the entire time span of data is

visualised for the selected location for all variables. The radio buttons above the time series plot allows the user to either compare the entire time span, or the two selected years on a monthly basis. **This CS allows the user to assess the past weather and climate conditions. This can be very helpful to better understand the conditions from the forecasts shown in the previous CS, as the user can relate it to already experienced conditions.**

Figure 4.1-4: Screenshot of the CS “Estaciones climáticas históricas” showing the observed data in all available weather stations. Clicking on a location in the map opens a time series plot for this particular weather station.

Very related to the previous CS is the CS “Estaciones climáticas históricas”. Instead of interpolated monthly values, it depicts the location of the weather stations in the study region. Once a station is selected, a time series plot is added underneath the map window. Different options of the radio buttons allow to compare the data for different purposes. Shown in [Figure 4.1-4](#) is the monthly statistic of a single year, but the visualisation can also show the entire time span, compare monthly values of two years, show an individual time span or the development of a single month over time. **This CS allows the user to assess the raw observations of past weather and climate conditions. This can, as for the interpolated CS, be very helpful to better understand the conditions from the forecasts shown in the previous CS, as the user can relate it to already experienced conditions. This CS also features more comparison options, than the interpolated flavour of it.**

Figure 4.1-5: Screenshot of the CS “Proyecciones climáticas” showing climate projections beyond 2040.

The tab “Proyecciones climáticas”, depicted in [Figure 4.1-5](#), shows climatic predictions of the variables temperature and precipitation. The time slider above the map allows the user to select a year of interest. It is important to note, that the simulation underlying this plot should not be seen as precise predictions for the selected year, but as a likely situation within these years. The selection of a location opens the time series plot visualising the development of the selected pixel over time. **This CS is useful to assess the mid-range future of changes in temperature and precipitation for Andalusia.**

Figure 4.1-6: Screenshot of the CS “Indicadores agroclimáticos” depicting the maximum number of consecutive dry days in spring 2011.

The CS “Indicadores agroclimáticos” goes beyond the main variables of temperature and precipitation and has been developed to visualise the indicators of i) maximum number of consecutive dry days, ii) maximum number of consecutive summer days and iii) number of summer days. While i) and ii) have a temporal resolution of seasons, the third indicator has a ten-day resolution. Clicking into the map selects a pixel and opens a time series plot under the map visualising the temporal development of this indicator. **This CS provides information that are directly related to plant health in the agricultural sector being an important source of information to plan adaptation measures.**

Figure 4.1-7: Screenshot of the CS “Información hidrológica”. The background map shown depicts a land use classification of the region. Overlaid are the groundwater measurement stations from two distinct networks.

This last CS focuses on the hydrology of the region “Los Pedroches”. It is titled “Información hidrológica” (Figure 4.1-7) and features a rich user interface to select different thematic base maps (radio buttons on the left) and a set of data layers to overlay on the base maps (checkboxes on the right). **This CS provides user tailored information to the water availability and hydrological structure of the region los pedroches. The provided information helps to better plan and prepare for drought situations in the region.**

Technical Summary

This CS is designed as several separate docker containers for back- and front-end components. It accesses data from different sources, mainly the Copernicus Data Store (CDS), data provided by project partner CREAFA as well as the ftp-server of SMHI. The back-end is developed around the library pygeoapi and utilises ZARR-Archives for storing data in S3-buckets of the Open Telecom Cloud. Additionally we also save Cloud Optimised Geotiffs (COGs) there. Each dataset creation and publishing follows OGC standards. Each data creation is implemented as an OGC API process and published as a collection. The front-end is based on Open Pioneer Trails utilising React and Openlayers as its key technologies for visualising time series data, the highcharts library has been utilised and customized.

In order to operate the CSs, two docker images, namely the trails frontend as well as the pygeoapi-ingestor-image need to be deployed along the cloud storage. During the first start, data is retrieved and stored in the s3 Buckets. Most text elements are stored in an i18n structure that allows for translation to different languages. Maps and charts are highly customized in the source code itself. For further technical information, please refer to the GitHub repositories:

https://github.com/icisk/llspain_trails

https://github.com/icisk/pygeoapi_ingestor

4.2. Emilia Romagna Living Lab (Italy, LL2)

User Manual

Service introduction and landing page

The [preoperational service for Emilia Romagna Living Lab](#) provides daily discharge forecasts for selected river sections, alongside historical context and management thresholds. The interface targets water managers and technicians in public/private entities such as irrigation consortia, hydropower operators, water utilities, as well as public authorities responsible for regulation and monitoring. No programming skills are required to use the service as will be clear in the following description. The landing page ([Figure 4.2-1](#)) combines station selection, available from both the list and the central map, and a chart panel on the right side. On selection of a station of interest, information is provided by the charts.

Figure 4.2-1: GUI landing page with station list (top and bottom zoom left), station position on the map (center and bottom zoom) and dashboard to activate specific graphs with access to station data and the forecasts available (top right).

Particularly, from this entry point the **discharge views and medium-range summaries** are accessible without leaving the page. The following figures show the current release of the GUI and the two key visualizations:

1. daily discharge forecasts Vs observed values.

Figure 4.2-2: Forecast discharges selectable through the GUI; custom forecast window daily has been chosen among available, with capability to activate-deactivate statistical forecast percentiles to improve legibility and understand forecast variability.

From the landing page, the user first selects the visualization type and, where available, the **forecast provider** (e.g. GLOFAS forecasts from [Copernicus](#)) that has been activated for the service.

[Figure 4.2-2](#) presents the **daily discharge view** for the selected station, where recent observations are **recorded and forecasted flows are plotted** on a common time axis. The display window is user-defined: preset **zoom ranges** above the chart and a **time slide** below allow inspection of the recent past and the selected forecast horizon in one continuous view. A concise legend distinguishes observations, the forecast median, and optional percentile bands; users can **toggle these bands to** expose or hide uncertainty as needed. Advanced ensemble views are available on demand, reflecting operator preferences for a clean operational chart.

Finally, **Threshold lines** provide immediate operational context. The chart can show indeed “above/below normal” bands and equivalent “extreme low” references, such as ecological-flow limits with seasonal variants; these markers are used to assess proximity to management triggers for activating or suspending withdrawals.

[Figure 4.2-4](#) below presents the **seasonal cumulative-volume view**. Forecast totals for the selected window are displayed **alongside the historical average** for the same period compared to the last ten years. Statistical variability is conveyed with box plots. The interactive legend allows enabling or disabling variability ranges, while a dropdown provides direct download of the underlying data in tabular form.

Figure 4.2-3:-Average forecast volumes in the coming season, provided versus historical average in the same period obtained from the last 10 years of observation, includes statistical variability in boxplot fashion.

Indeed, both visualizations support export. The service can produce compact outputs in standard graphic formats (e.g., PNG for charts) and in tabular form (e.g., CSV for daily or cumulative strips) **for routine reporting**, board briefings, and bulletins to end users such as associated farmers or industrial water users.

Example use case: Land Reclamation Consortium for withdrawal management in the incoming season

This didactic scenario illustrates a typical end-to-end session with the service and how its outputs may support withdrawal decisions.

In early June, the planner opens the landing page (Figure 4.2-1), selects the active forecast provider (e.g., Copernicus GLOFAS), and chooses the station of interest (e.g., Lugo), whose incoming discharge governs activation and suspension of withdrawals under the applicable protocol.

The **daily discharge** view (Figure 4.2.4) is activated to display the next-weeks forecast against reference conditions and “below-normal” bands aligned with the summer **lower ecological-flow** threshold. The median forecast (50th percentile) trends toward the “below-normal” band within two weeks, implying a likely suspension shortly after.

Figure 4.2-4: The daily forecast accessed by the user for the selected station compared to the relevant thresholds.

To quantify risk, the planner enables percentile bands he his reasonably and safely, confident with (Figure 4.2-5). and evaluates the probability of crossing the lower ecological value. Given a high crossing likelihood, the **emergency procedure is triggered**: pre-filling channel storage in the coming week to secure a few extra irrigation days after suspension.

Figure 4.2-5: Toggling on uncertainty of the probabilistic forecast to get confidence level.

The planner then opens the **cumulative-volume** view (Figure 4) on a seasonal window and compares expected totals against the decadal box plots. Despite forecast variability, the totals align reasonably well with the historical average, which reinforces both the decision to prepare for suspension and the messaging to end users.

The bulletin to farmers and/or industrial users states that a temporary suspension is **probable**, notes that emergency storage has been **activated** to enable selective irrigation and announces that an updated forecast and bulletin will be issued at the start of next month.

Finally, the planner exports a PNG of the daily chart and a CSV of the underlying series for internal circulation, bulletin preparation, and formal communication to the authority. This documentation step is required before extraordinary storage can proceed, as the service has been **pre-validated by the authority** and the emergency protocol jointly signed.

Ex-post, during autumn–winter, observed vs forecast flows are reviewed monthly to **compute false alarms, hits, and misses**, and to refine both the protocol and the decision chain for the next season.

4.3. Rijnland Living Lab (Netherlands, LL3)

User Manual

The solution in the Rijnland living lab allows a pre selection depending on the application area (Recreatievaart = recreational boating, Landbouw = agriculture, Waterbeheer = watermanagement, Boomteelt = tree nursery) on the landing page of the CS (Figure 4.3.1, left). A total of four different climate information services have been developed in co-design with users (Droogtebeeld = drought situation, Afvoer Lobith = Lobith discharge, Neerslagtekort = precipitation deficit, Klimaat = climate). By clicking on each of the buttons, the CS is opened in the same browser tab where the “Menu” button on the top left of the screen will bring the user back to the landing page.

Figure 4.3-1: Left: Landing page for the CS for the selected role of “Waterbeheer”. Right: Summary calendar week view of the drought situation in the Rijnland region.

In the “Droogtebeeld” view (Figure 4.3-1, right), the most compact information display is chosen to provide a quick overview of the current situation and the weekly forecast. Depending on the values of the precipitation deficit (the largest daily value in the region for the considered calendar week) or the discharge of the Rhine near Lobith, an assessment is made as to whether and how severe a drought is. The color scale of the drought indicator ranges from blue to green and orange in a total of seven classes to red. The calendar week display and the map of the precipitation deficit (Figure 4.3-2) use the same breaks and colors. **Based on the “Droogtebeeld” view, users can quickly grasp the current drought situation and will get a brief and user group specific explanation of the driving factors. Based on severity and interest, users can then dive into more details with the subsequent CS.**

Figure 4.3-2: Combined map and time series representation of the precipitation deficit. The map shows the precipitation deficit on September 1, 2025, starting on April 1, 2025. The time series shows the development for the point selected on the map (denoted by a red circle with black border) from April 1, 2025, to the current date (here, September 1, 2025) and the forecast of the precipitation deficit based on a weather simulation from the Copernicus service for the next two months.

The “Neerslagtekort” combines an interactive map and a time series view of the spatiotemporal precipitation deficit data (Figure 4.3-2). The presented values are based on recorded data as well as 6 month forecasts of temperature and precipitation which are used to calculate each day's precipitation deficit. Every day we recalculate the values based on the latest observed precipitation deficit. A 1 km resolution raster is used for the calculation. The map view can be controlled by the time slider overlaid at the top of the map window. The soldier starts at 1st April while the two buttons on the right of the time slider allow to select the year (this prototype only features data for 2024 and 2025). The map also allows pan and zoom, while the provided data encloses the Netherlands. The time series view is based on the selected year and location from the above map window in the CS. It shows the local development of the precipitation deficit based on recorded data and gives an outlook based on weather simulations obtained from Copernicus for the coming two months. **This CS view allows the user to explore the precipitation deficit at specific locations and regions. Based on the ensemble forecast, stakeholders can plan ahead and take actions to e.g., save and store water way ahead of time.**

Figure 4.3-3: Screenshot of the CS “Afvoer Lobith” showing the runoff of the river Rhine near Lobith. The time series plot shows measured runoff and monthly updated predictions of the runoff based on 51 Ensemble members. The horizontal red dashed line indicates the low water threshold which once fallen below calls for action.

“Afvoer Lobith” (Figure 4.3-3) provides information essential to the water management, as this is the main inlet of riverine water to the Netherlands providing water to the channel network. Therefore, the CS “Afvoer Lobith” visualises the recent (past two months) recorded run-off together with weather simulations entailing 51 ensemble members entering SMHI’s [European HYPE runoff model](#) for the next five months. The horizontal red dashed line marks the threshold of low water which varies over the year. If the runoff falls below this threshold, the water management is inclined to take measures in adapting to the water shortage. The user can also switch between the visualisation with confidence bands as in Figure 4.3-3 and visualising the runoff prediction based on the single ensemble members. Furthermore, the switch on lower right allows to toggle the visualisation of the recorded runoff values. On mouse over, the user will be able to read the exact values from a pop-up in the time series plot. **Based on this CS, regional water managers in Rijnland can assess the recent and forecasted volume of water entering the Netherlands through the Rhine to prepare way ahead of time for mitigation measures in case of expected low water conditions.**

The view “Klimaat”, also directly accessible from the “Afvoer Lobith” time series plot, summarises in a combination of text and figures the relationship between a changing climate and drought. This CS envisions and describes the situation in Rijnland around the year 2100. It serves as a source of information to assess the future situation and to initiate discussions preparing actions for the future. The summary is based on climatic information provided by KNMI (<https://www.knmi.nl/klimaat>). **While the other views focus on short and midterm forecasts, this view allows to look further into the future, motivating larger and more rigid, but well informed measures of climate adaptation.**

Technical Summary

This CS is designed as several separate docker containers for back- and front-end components. It accesses data from different APIs such as Copernicus Data Store (CDS) or the Royal Dutch Meteorological Institute (KNMI) as well as the ftp-server of SMHI. The back-end is developed around the library pygeoapi and utilises ZARR-Archives for storing data in S3-buckets of the Open Telecom Cloud. Each dataset creation and publishing follows OGC standards. Each data creation is implemented as an OGC API process and published as a collection. The front-end is based on Open Pioneer Trails utilising React and Openlayers as its key technologies for visualising time series data, the [highcharts](#) library has been utilised and customized.

In order to operate the CSs, two docker images, namely the trails frontend as well as the pygeoapi-ingestor-image need to be deployed along the cloud storage. During the first start, data is retrieved and stored in the s3 Buckets. Most text elements are stored in an i18n structure that allows for translation to different languages. Maps and charts are highly customized in the source code itself. For further technical information, please refer to the GitHub repositories:

<https://github.com/icisk/LL7-NL>

4.4. Crete Island Living Lab (Greece, LL4)

User Manual

The Living Lab of Crete, Greece, supports the adaptation and development of the tourism sector; it does so through a multi-sectorial approach, that addresses informational needs of other sectors as well, i.e. water management, transportation and energy.

The developed service addresses the sectorial needs at different temporal and spatial scales, which are provided through a web-based platform for the entire Island of Crete available through the I-CISK landing page or directly at <https://icisk.emvis.gr>, and are categorized in the following 4 sections (Figure 4.4-1):

- **Seasonal Indicators for Tourism:** Seasonal forecasts obtained by ECMWF's SEAS probabilistic model, are repurposed into a series of essential meteorological variables and other tourism-related indicators for Crete.
- **Hydrological Indicators:** Seasonal Hydrological forecasting workflow provided by HYPE model allows for the estimation of river discharges at each hydrological catchment for 7-months ahead.
- **Water management service for OAK:** Hydrological forecasts are further repurposed to calculate the expected volume of water during the upcoming wet period for specific reservoirs intended for potable water, that are of special interest for OAK.
- **Climate projections:** Specific essential climatic variables and tourism indicators are also calculated for future decades (until 2100) based on 8 combinations of Global and Regional climate models, to support long-term planning adaptation measures.

Figure 4.4-1: Initial screen of the Living Lab of Crete developed in I-CISK.

Seasonal Indicators for Tourism

This service contains essential meteorological variables and other tourism-related indicators for a forecasting horizon of 7 months, updated on a monthly basis (Figure 4.4-2).

Figure 4.4-2: Initial screen of Seasonal Indicators service.

The indicators are grouped into four categories as presented in the following overview:

<p>Essential Climatic Variables</p> <p>Seasonal forecasts of climatic variables (e.g. temperature, precipitation) are obtained from ECMWF through Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)</p>
<p>Temperature. Forecasts of average air temperature aggregated on a 15 days reference period for the next 7 months. Updated once a month on the 6th. Precipitation. Forecasts of average daily precipitation aggregated on a 15 days reference period for the next 7 months. Updated once a month on the 6th.</p>
<p>Climatic Tourism Indicators</p> <p>Easy-to-understand metrics that provide specialized and tailored information to activities related to tourism</p>
<p>Tourism Climatic Index. The Tourism Climatic Index (TCI) evaluates the climate favorability for outdoor tourism by combining seven climatic variables related to the human comfort levels. TCI is calculated on a 0 to 100 scale. Values close to 0 represent unfavorable conditions, while values close to 100 represent ideal conditions. Light Precipitation Frequency. Frequency of days that daily precipitation exceeds 1 mm. High Precipitation Frequency. Frequency of days that daily precipitation exceeds 10 mm. Extreme Precipitation Frequency. Frequency of days that daily precipitation exceeds 50 mm. Frequency of Extreme Hot Days. This indicator is calculated by the number of days that the Maximum daily temperature exceeded 35 °C, and it is expressed as a percentage over the reference period (15 days). Frequency of Tropical Nights. This indicator is calculated by the number of days that the Minimum daily temperature did not drop below 20 °C, and it is expressed as a percentage over the reference period (15 days). Cooling Degree Days. Cooling Degree Days (CDD) are a measure of how much (in degrees), and for how long (in days), outside air temperature was higher than a specific base temperature, and is directly related to the energy demand for cooling residential buildings. CDD is calculated using a base temperature of 25 °C, and assuming that no cooling is needed when the outside temperature is below this threshold. CDD are calculated for a period of 15 days and are presented as the daily average for that period.</p>
<p>Infrastructure Indicators</p> <p>Indicators related with critical infrastructure that may affect tourism activities</p>
<p>Instability Index. The instability index is used to quantify the susceptibility and hazard of landslides and slope failures in a specific area. The index is calculated taking into consideration multiple factors (e.g., soil properties, slope inclination, geology, rainfall conditions) and is calculated in a 0 to 100 scale (higher values denote a higher risk of landslides).</p>
<p>Marine navigation</p> <p>Seasonal indicators from ECMWF ocean modelling that affect port operations</p>
<p>Frequency of Strong N&NW Winds. Frequency of days that North and Northwest wind gusts exceed 7 Beauforts. Frequency of Strong S Winds. Frequency of days that South wind gusts exceed 7 Beauforts. Significant height (wind + swell). This is the significant height of combined wind waves and sea swell measured in meters. Mean wave direction. Direction of surface waves considering both wind-sea waves and sea swell. This parameter is the average of all frequencies and directions of the 2D wave spectrum. Mean wave period. The average time (in seconds) it takes for two consecutive wave crests on the sea surface to pass through a fixed point. Averaging is applied over all frequencies and directions of the 2D wave spectrum.</p>

Available parameters and indicators are grouped into 4 categories, which can be selected by the user through different drop-down menus (Figure 4.4-3). The spatial and temporal variation of each indicator is presented through maps and timeseries graphs. By clicking at any point at the map the value of the selected indicator for the point of interest is displayed. The user can navigate through different dates of the forecasting horizon by selecting the appropriate date in the time bar at the bottom of the screen (Figure 4.4-4). For each indicator, maps are available at 15 days intervals for a forecasting horizon of 7 months ahead.

Selection of indicator category.

Selection of indicator.

Spatial variation of each indicator is presented through a map component.

Maps are available for 7 months ahead, at 15 days intervals. Users can navigate through the timebar at the bottom of the screen.

Figure 4.4-3: Selection of seasonal indicator and map interactions.

Figure 4.4-4: Graph of the temporal variation of the selected indicator (Frequency of North Winds > 7BF) for the next 7 months.

Hydrological Indicators

This service aims to address water allocation needs, by providing seasonal forecasting of river discharges through hydrological forecasting. A large ensemble of 51 members of climate forecasts is used from the ECMWF's SEAS model as forcing in the HYPE hydrological model. The initial screen of the service is presented at the following figure (Figure 4.4-5).

Figure 4.4-5: Initial screen of **Hydrological Indicators** service.

The results of the hydrological model are available at each catchment of Crete (42 catchments in total). By clicking on a catchment, a graph presenting the variation of the river discharge for the next 7 months is displayed on the screen (Figure 4.4-6). The graph is able to display the individual ensemble members of the hydrological simulation as well as their statistical properties displayed as box plots (Figure 4.4-7).

Figure 4.4-6: The forecasts of river discharge are presented as time series (aggregated at 15-days intervals) for the forecasting horizon of 7 months, along with their statistical properties.

Display of the individual 51 members of the ensemble hydrological forecast.

Statistical properties of the forecast as box-plots displaying the **maximum**, the **75th percentile**, the **mean** (red line), the **median**, the **25th percentile** and the **minimum** of the ensemble.

Figure 4.4-7: Individual members and statistical properties of the hydrological ensemble.

Water management service for OAK

The service is based on providing a forecast for the volume of water expected to enter reservoirs used for drinking purposes, during the upcoming wet period i.e. Nov-Dec-Jan-Feb. This service is customized for OAK, i.e. the manager of Crete's water bodies, which needs to plan the allocation of water resources between tourism, agriculture and other critical water demanding sectors. This procedure takes place in early spring and OAK used to rely on historical data in order to estimate the future water availability of each reservoir. The developed service allows OAK to take decisions using seasonal hydrological forecasts to estimate the volume of incoming water, and evaluate different strategies for each reservoir according to its potential during the wet period. The initial page of the water management service is presented in the following figure (Figure 4.4-8).

Figure 4.4-8: Initial screen of the Water Management Service for OAK end user.

The graph in Figure 4.4-8 displays the most recent estimation for the total volume of water in hm³ expected to enter each one of the five reservoirs (Amari, Aposelemis, Bramianos, Phaneromeni, Plakiotissa) used for drinking water purposes in Crete.

In a separate graph the user can compare the current forecast of river discharges with historical simulated hydrological data from the period 1980-2020. The comparison allows the user to be able characterize the current hydrological year as normal, wet, dry, etc. (Figure 4.4-9 a). A separate graph (Figure 4.4-9 panel b) displays how the estimation for the total volume of water expected in each reservoir during the wet period changes, as hydrological forecasts are being updated.

a) The graph displays that the current forecast of b) Latest forecast of water volume expected river discharge (red dotted line) for the selected during the wet period (red dot), and expired catchment is below the 20th percentile of historical forecasts (orange dots). river discharges

Figure 4.4-9: Customized views of the Water Management Service for OAK.

Climate projections

Beyond the seasonal time scale, the Living Lab of Crete offers insights into the evolution of key climatic variables and tourism-related indicators over the coming decades, enabling users to assess and plan long-term adaptation measures (Figure 10). Climatic projections are obtained from the Copernicus Climate Data Store and processed for multiple parameters and indicators at a spatial resolution of $0.11^\circ \times 0.11^\circ$, which are available for whole Greece.

For each indicator, results are provided from seven combinations of Global and Regional Climate Models (GCM–RCM), along with the ensemble mean. The projections are based on CORDEX climate experiments using the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), specifically RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5, which span a wide range of plausible climate futures.

Figure 4.4-10: Initial screen of the Climate Projections service.

The user selects the parameter, and the relevant indicator from a drop-down menu, together with a series of other options needed (Figure 4.4-11) for the map to be displayed on the right panel. The values in the maps and graphs can be presented either as "Absolute" values or as "Relative" change from a historical baseline 1980-2005 (Figure 4.4-12).

1) Selection of Parameter category

3) Selection of Global and Regional climate models

2) Selection of Indicator or Variable

4) Selection of Representative Concentration Pathways RCPs and Time horizon.

Figure 4.4-11: Steps for selecting an indicator and displaying the climate projections map.

Figure 4.4-12. Toggler for displaying map values as absolute or relative.

Technical Summary

The Crete Living Lab provides integrated services that support tourism while also addressing related domains such as water management, transportation, and energy. Indicators are delivered through a web-based platform (<https://icisk.emvis.gr>) covering the entire island of Crete, offering both seasonal forecasts and long-term climate insights.

The platform provides four main categories of services:

- **Seasonal Tourism Indicators:** Based on ECMWF SEAS forecasts, processed into essential climatic variables (temperature, precipitation) and tourism-specific metrics such as the Tourism Climatic Index (TCI), precipitation frequency, tropical nights, and cooling degree days. Infrastructure-related indicators (e.g., instability index) and marine navigation parameters (e.g., wind gust frequencies, wave height) are also included.
- **Hydrological Indicators:** Seasonal river discharge forecasts generated by the HYPE hydrological model, driven by ECMWF ensemble climate forecasts, are available at 42 hydrological catchments across Crete. Users can explore ensemble statistics and temporal variations through interactive maps and timeseries graphs.
- **Water Management Service for OAK:** Customized forecasts for the regional water authority (OAK) estimate expected reservoir inflows during the wet season, supporting decisions on potable water allocation across competing sectors such as tourism and agriculture. Comparisons with historical hydrological simulations enable classification of hydrological years and monitoring of forecast updates.
- **Climate Projections:** Long-term projections up to 2100 provide essential climate variables and tourism indicators under multiple GCM–RCM combinations and RCP scenarios (4.5 and 8.5), supporting adaptation planning.

The platform integrates data from ECMWF SEAS, SMHI HYPE model, Copernicus Climate Data Store and local datasets. The backend employs Django, PostgreSQL with PostGIS, and GeoServer, with automated workflows for data processing and updates. The frontend is developed in React with Leaflet and Chart.js, providing an intuitive interface for map-based exploration and time series visualization.

4.5. Budapest Living Lab (Hungary, LL5)

User Manual

The Living Lab in Budapest focuses on the study and management of the urban heat island (UHI) phenomenon in Hungary and the Carpathian Basin. The region has a temperate continental climate (Köppen classification: Dfb), with warm to hot summers and cold winters. Temperatures across the Carpathian Basin are rising faster than the European average, and the area is increasingly prone to droughts and heat waves.

The Living Lab focuses on three primary sectors: tourism, healthcare, and urban planning. Budapest's many cultural heritage sites attract a significant number of tourists during the summer months, but the increased number of extremely hot days has a negative impact on tourism. Heat islands and increased nighttime temperatures, especially in urban environments, have a number of negative effects on human health.

Budapest Living Lab takes an innovative approach to urban heat mapping, combining high-tech solutions with community participation. At the heart of the project is the CityZcan platform, which provides a comprehensive urban heat monitoring system with street-level measurements and addressing following objectives:

- Raise awareness of urban heat risks.
- Support public health planning (e.g., hospitals, elderly care).
- Provide early warning of heatwaves to the public.
- Assist urban planners and energy managers in climate adaptation.

Accessing the Service

The Budapest Living Lab climate services are primarily accessible through the **CityZcan platform** at <https://i-cisk.dev.52north.org/living-labs/budapest--hu/> and <https://city.zcan.eu/>. The web interface provides multiple entry points for different user needs and technical expertise levels.

Landing Page

The main landing page (<https://city.zcan.eu/>) serves as the central hub for all Budapest Living Lab services. Users can navigate to different sections of the platform, including interactive maps, documentation, and downloadable applications. The interface is designed to accommodate both technical users and general stakeholders from urban planning, tourism, and health sectors.

Figure 4.5-1: Screenshot of the landing page of the CityZcan Webpage.

Interactive Heat Mapping Interface

The core visualization tool is accessible at city.zcan.eu/osm-orto-heat-layers.html providing:

- **Multi-layer visualization:** Users can toggle between orthophotos, thermal images, predicted thermal maps, and OpenStreetMap base layers
- **Zoom and pan controls:** Standard map navigation tools for exploring the Terézváros and Erzsébetváros districts in Budapest
- **Layer switching:** Interactive controls to compare different data sources and timeframes
- **Temperature readings:** Click-based temperature value extraction from thermal imagery

Figure 4.5-2: Examples of two map layers for the Terézváros district in Budapest under study. The upper map shows the observed thermal image, while the lower map depicts the output of the CNN based on an ortho image.

Documentation Repository for Sensors

Comprehensive user guides and technical documentation are available at city.zcan.eu/documents/ including:

- User manuals for the sensor box
- Technical specifications for developers

Gamification site

Thermaform Your City (<https://city.zcan.eu/thermaform-your-city/>), an **interactive educational game** that engages users in learning about urban heat mitigation strategies through gamified city planning scenarios, supporting the platform's commitment to making climate adaptation accessible through innovative educational tools. The system is accessible through modern browsers without registration requirements, while advanced functionalities are supported by comprehensive technical documentation and assistance from the ICISK and IDEAS teams.

Downloadable Applications

CityZcanView Plugin

Download Location: <https://city.zcan.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/CityZcanView.zip>

The CityZcanView application is an open-source plugin for the Fiji image processing platform. To access this tool:

1. **Prerequisites:** Install Fiji (ImageJ) on your system
2. **Download:** Extract the CityZcanView.zip file
3. **Installation:** Follow the provided installation instructions within the zip package
4. **Functionality:**
 - Open .tiff files from Lepton 3.5 sensors
 - Real-time temperature reading capabilities
 - One-click export of color-scaled, annotated PNG files
 - Scientific-grade image analysis tools

Thermal Image Analysis Scripts

Script Repository: <https://city.zcan.eu/heat-map-analysis-sripts/>

Advanced users and researchers can access the heat map analysis scripts for:

- Custom data processing workflows
- Integration with existing urban planning systems
- Academic research applications
- Extended analysis capabilities beyond the web interface

Applications Gallery and Dataset Archive

The platform maintains a continuously evolving applications gallery at city.zcan.eu/apps/ that serves as a dynamic repository for climate service tools and resources. This gallery represents a living platform that will continue to expand throughout the project lifecycle and beyond, ensuring long-term sustainability and continued innovation in urban heat island research. The applications gallery includes a dedicated section for measured thermal data (raw data), providing researchers, developers, and stakeholders with access to the complete thermal datasets collected during the Budapest Living Lab campaigns including:

- Original drone thermal imagery in full resolution provided in GeoTIFF format
- Ground-level thermal measurements from mobile thermal cameras and sensor networks

Data Accessibility and Standards

To ensure maximum compatibility, data is provided in internationally recognized, standardized open formats such as GeoTIFF and CSV. Comprehensive metadata and quality assurance documentation accompany all datasets.

System Requirements

Web Interface Access

- Browser compatibility: Modern web browsers (Chrome, Firefox, Safari, Edge)
- Internet connection: Broadband recommended for smooth map tile loading
- Device support: Desktop, tablet, and mobile devices with responsive design
- No registration required: Open access to basic visualization tools

CityZcanView Application

- Operating system: Windows, macOS, or Linux
- Fiji/ImageJ: Latest version recommended
- Java: Java 8 or higher
- RAM: Minimum 4GB recommended for large thermal image processing
- Storage: Variable, depending on dataset size

User Authentication and Access Levels

The Budapest Living Lab employs a tiered access approach where not all data is directly available on the platform, but can be provided on request. The public access (without registration) provides:

- Basic web interface navigation
- Standard heat map visualization
- General documentation access
- Educational materials

Support and Feedback

- Contact: I-CISK Team (info@icisk.eu) and IDEAS Team (info@ideas-science.com)
- Project website: icisk.eu and city.zcan.eu

Summary and Outlook

The Budapest Living Lab focuses on urban heat island (UHI) management in Hungary within the temperate continental climate of the Carpathian Basin, specifically targeting the tourism, healthcare, and urban planning sectors. The innovative CityZcan platform (city.zcan.eu) combines high-tech thermal monitoring with community participation, providing comprehensive street-level heat measurements. The Living Lab's primary objectives include raising awareness of urban heat risks, supporting public health planning with early heatwave warnings, and assisting urban planners and energy managers in climate adaptation strategies.

The service is primarily accessible through web-based interfaces, where the interactive heat mapping tool (city.zcan.eu/osm-orto-heat-layers.html) offers multi-layer visualization with orthophotos, thermal images, and CNN predictions for Budapest's Terézváros and Erzsébetváros districts. The platform provides an open-source CityZcanView plugin for the Fiji image processing system for thermal image analysis, along with analysis scripts and a continuously evolving applications gallery (city.zcan.eu/apps/) that includes a complete thermal dataset archive with open data formats (GeoTIFF, CSV) for researchers and developers. The system is accessible through modern browsers without registration requirements, while advanced functionalities are supported by comprehensive technical documentation and assistance from the ICISK and IDEAS teams.

While the I-CISK project officially concludes in 2025, the Budapest Living Lab represents a foundation for continued research and development. The platform is designed with long-term sustainability in mind, ensuring that the valuable datasets, tools, and methodologies developed during the project remain accessible and continue to evolve.

Transition to BEHOLDER Project

The Budapest Living Lab development team is committed to extending the project's impact through transition to the BEHOLDER project (beholderproject.com), which will build upon the established infrastructure and methodologies. This continuity ensures that:

- Existing tools and datasets remain accessible and continue to receive updates and maintenance
- New research findings from the BEHOLDER project will be integrated into the platform
- Enhanced capabilities and additional climate services will be developed based on lessons learned from the I-CISK implementation
- International collaboration networks established during I-CISK will be maintained and expanded

How the results can be reused

- Budapest Living Lab data can be integrated into third-party GIS supporting existing urban planning workflows
- Open-source architecture can benefit from community contributions and custom tool development
- Citizen science tools can be used to engage public participation in urban heat monitoring

4.6. Alazani River basin Living Lab (Georgia, LL6)

User Manual

This User Manual describes the pre-operational service for the [Alazani River basin Living Lab](#) and its main functions. It lists the data sources and components available from the landing page and explains basic navigation. It covers Hydro Forecasts, SPI-3 drought maps, and Temperature & Precipitation, including visualization and data export.

Hydro Forecast

Data and providers. The component consumes SMHI and [GLOFAS](#) hydrological ensembles and ERA5/Copernicus products. Where multiple providers are available, the active source can be selected from the dropdown on the right. Forecasts are bias-adjusted and, when applicable, downscaled to local points of interest to increase operational relevance.

Time-series view (daily hydrograph).

From the landing page, select a basin section and monitoring station using the left panel. The central map confirms the location, while the right panel opens the **Hydro Forecasts** view. The chart overlays recent observations and the forecast median on a common time axis. Percentile bands (e.g., 5–95%, 10–90%) depict forecast uncertainty. Reference lines such as **Above Normal** and **Extreme High** support quick screening and can be toggled on or off via the interactive legend above the plot. Zoom controls are provided both above the chart (fixed windows: 1, 3, 6 months, or full season) and below the chart via a time slider for precise interval selection ([Figure 4.6-1](#)).

Cumulative-volumes view (seasonal average discharges)

Choose **Cumulative volumes** from the visualization dropdown on the right. This view presents forecast seasonal totals alongside observed values for the current month and variability ranges expressed as box plots derived from the last years for the same period. Daily values for the selected month are listed beneath the chart for direct inspection ([Figure 4.6-2](#)).

The interactive legend enables or disables percentile bands to control how much statistical variability is displayed. A dropdown menu offers direct download of the current chart as PNG and the underlying data as CSV for reports and bulletins ([Figure 4.6-2](#)).

Figure 4.6-1: Screenshots of the GUI landing page with station list (top left), station position on the map (top and bottom left as zoom in) and dashboard to activate specific graphs with access to station data and the forecasts available (top right and bottom right as zoom in).

Figure 4.6-2: Screenshots of the hydro forecast component _ average monthly graph.

SPI index

The **SPI index** component of the Service, accessible by the left panel, provides drought monitoring and outlook as interrogable maps. Two modes are available: Historical SPI-3, computed from [ERA5-Land](#) reanalysis as a long-term reference, and Seasonal SPI-3, derived, among others, from [Copernicus seasonal forecasts](#) for forward-looking assessment. Selection between **historical and forecast datasets** is available from the left panel directly .

Each map **displays SPI-3 values** for the chosen month across the Alazani-Iori region. Colours encode standard SPI classes from drought to wet conditions. Historical maps show the current status relative to the 1980–2010 climatology; seasonal maps show projected anomalies for the selected target month. Updates run monthly through an automated process (Figure 4.6-3). SPI-3 is calculated by fitting a gamma distribution to monthly precipitation in the 1980–2010 reference, adjusting for zero-precipitation probability, and transforming to a standard normal variable (Z-score). Historical SPI uses ERA5 monthly means and hourly data; seasonal SPI uses Copernicus seasonal forecast precipitation. The pipeline builds OGC collections at $\sim 0.1^\circ$ grid resolution.

How to use the map. Choose Historical or Seasonal SPI from the dataset dropdown, then pick the month (and lead, when in seasonal forecast mode). The map supports pan and zoom.

Figure 4.6-3: SPI-3 index. Upper panel: historical SPI-3 map for the current month (1980–2010 climate reference). Lower panel: forecast SPI-3 map for the selected target month. The time-slice bar at the bottom lets you scroll through the months of the upcoming season. The color scale follows standard SPI classes; the interactive legend allows toggling anomaly ranges.

Temperature and precipitation

From the landing page, select **Temperature & Precipitation** in the left menu, then choose a location from the station list or by clicking the central map. The map returns the value for the **nearest grid cell** at the provider's native resolution; for Copernicus seasonal forecasts this is approximately $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ (dataset: **C3S seasonal-original-single-levels**), ([Figure 4.6-4](#), top)

The upper chart displays **monthly mean 2 m air temperature** for the next six months. Each month is shown as an ensemble distribution with a marked **median** and variability bands, so the expected thermal regime and its uncertainty are immediately readable across the season.

The lower chart presents **monthly total precipitation** in millimetres over the same six-month horizon. As above, each month appears as an ensemble distribution with **median** and variability bands, allowing wet or dry tendencies to be evaluated alongside temperature. ([Figure 4.6-4](#), bottom)

An **Export** dropdown next to the charts lets you download the current view as a PNG image and the underlying data as a CSV table for reporting and further analysis. Provider selection and month stepping follow the same controls used elsewhere in the service.

Monthly Forecast for Temperature and Precipitation at confluence point, Municipalità di Kvareli, Cachezia, Georgia

Figure 4.6-4: Temperature & Precipitation module. Top: landing page with the Temperature & Precipitation selector on the left, interactive map in the center for choosing the location (nearest grid cell at provider resolution), and the chart panel on the right. Bottom: zoomed charts. The upper chart shows monthly mean air temperature at 2 m for the next six months with ensemble variability bands and the median. The lower chart shows monthly total precipitation (mm) over the same temporal horizon, also with variability bands and the median. Both charts support legend toggles and an export dropdown as PNG- or CSV-files.

Example use case: Farmer in Kvareli Municipality

This farmer scenario is **didactic**. It illustrates a typical, theory-based use of the Alazani–Iori service by summarising needs and practices identified through the Georgian MAP consultations and interviews. Those activities highlighted agriculture as the main livelihood, a demand for water-availability and drought information to guide allocation and planning, and farmer strategies that combine short-term coping and longer-term adaptation

In early spring the farmer opens the **Hydro Forecasts** view from the landing page, selects a station (e.g. Shakriani #440 as in [Figure 4.6-1](#)) and the active provider, then reads the ensemble hydrograph over 1 – 3 months with **median** and **percentile bands**. “Above Normal” and “Extreme High” reference lines help to screen for high-flow episodes; zoom controls set the operational window. If the median and spread indicate below-normal flows through May–October, the farmer advances canal cleaning, schedules night irrigation, or shifts planting and harvest dates to reduce exposure during peak demand.

Next, the farmer opens the **SPI-3 maps** ([Figure 4.6-3](#)) to verify spatial drought signals for the current and target months in the farm’s sub-basin. A dry classification strengthens the decision to pay for supplemental irrigation where channels are available and to adjust tillage to conserve soil moisture.

For the seasonal outlook, the farmer switches to **Cumulative volumes** and to **Temperature & Precipitation**. Monthly **min/max temperature** and **total precipitation** ([Figure 4.6-4](#)) are shown as box plots with medians for the next six months; if hot and dry distributions persist, the farmer locks early harvest windows and defers non-essential plantings. If dryness is recurrent year-on-year, the farmer considers drip irrigation or a small well as longer-term measures, consistent with reported adaptation pathways.

Finally, the farmer exports charts as PNG-files and tables as CSV-files from the **Export** dropdown to attach evidence to cooperative bulletins and input orders. Over autumn and winter, observed versus forecast outcomes are reviewed to refine thresholds and timing — an approach aligned with the LL aim to enrich agrometeorological bulletins with streamflow, temperature, precipitation, and drought indicators.

4.7. Lesotho Living Lab (LL7)

User Manual

Introduction

The Lesotho Climate Service delivers seasonal drought information to support climate-smart decisions. It uses the **Precipitation Drought Index (PDI)** to assess the likelihood and severity of drought in upcoming seasons and is intended for farmers, local authorities, and operational planners.

There are **two deployments** of the same service logic:

- **Public I-CISK portal** ([demo](#)): a gentle introduction to the concept, variables, and core interactions investigated in the Living Lab. It offers open, climate-only access for exploration.
- **Operational IBF platform**: the Impact-Based Forecasting (IBF) environment run with the Lesotho Red Cross. It contains the production pipelines, trigger workflows, and decision products required for day-to-day operations.

How this manual is organised. The first part briefly documents the public demonstration interface (landing page, map, season selection, legend). The second part describes the operational features of highest relevance that are implemented in the **IBF** version. For implementation and maintenance details of the operational setup on IBF, see also the open-source repositories: [rodekruis/IBF-system \(platform\)](#) and [rodekruis/IBF-drought-pipeline \(drought workflow\)](#).

Demo on Public I-CISK portal

On the public I-CISK portal, the Lesotho Climate Service offers examples of seasonal drought maps and statistics which supports agricultural planning, and enables preparedness for water resources management.

From the landing view (Figure 4.7-1), the user may above all choose the season or forecast run to analyze (with the time slider at the bottom of the map)

The center map of Lesotho displays the drought signal computed with the Precipitation Drought Index (PDI); colors represent categories from normal to extreme drought.

A dataset selector (on the bottom right of the map) lets you pick the variable of interest among available ones;

On the left a legend explains classes and thresholds. Furthermore time-series graph on the left allow inspection of statistical variability of forecasted values of the Drought index.

On the public I-CISK portal, the Lesotho Climate Service presents seasonal **drought maps and basic statistics** to support agricultural planning and preparedness. From the landing view (Figure 5) you select the target season or forecast run with the **time slider** below the map.

The central map displays the **Precipitation Drought Index (PDI)** as the **probability that seasonal rainfall falls in the lower tercile** of its historical distribution, computed from ECMWF SEAS5 ensembles; colours encode categories from normal to extreme drought and a side legend explains the thresholds.

Figure 4.7-2: Impact-Based Forecasting (IBF) Portal overview. Left panel: run time, user info, quick links (Alert log, IBF guide, trigger explanation, Export), and notes on past alerts. Top bar: portal title and account controls. Main section: 12-month timeline, forecast summary, and interactive district map. Optional layers: Red Cross branches, population, exposed population, and probability of below-normal rainfall. Legend highlights triggered areas.

In the IBF portal the **workflow** moves through **No-Trigger**, **Warning**, and **Trigger** states (Figure 4.7-3), with the Warning view summarizing expected timing and source, listing at-risk districts and exposed population, shading affected districts on the map, highlighting the rainy-season window on the 12-month timeline, and offering a **Set Trigger** action when “Drought ongoing” applies; when Trigger is confirmed by an authorized Lesotho Red Cross Society (LRCS) coordinator the banner switches state, triggered districts are outlined, and notifications are automatically sent to all users sent to start starting early action plans and mobilizing resources

Risk is computed from the probability that seasonal rainfall falls in the **lower tercile** of the historical distribution by counting ensemble members at or below the threshold and dividing by 51; a **district is flagged if at least 10%** of its area exceeds the probability threshold, and exposed population is the sum of people within those pixels; two indicators are available and country-configurable: **1-month seasonal rainfall and 3-month rolling accumulation**.

The map uses symbology keyed to below-normal rainfall probability and exposed population, supports layer toggles and district inspection, and is paired with a forecast summary above and a one-year timeline from “today.”

The service includes scenario tooling to run **Warning/NoWarning/Forecast** tests on schedule with each ECMWF monthly release.

Figure 4.7-3: Impact-Based Forecasting Portal Warning state example (“Drought ongoing”). Left panel lists timing, source, at-risk districts, and exposed population; map highlights affected districts; 12-month timeline marks the rainy-season window; banner provides Set Trigger to confirm activation. Export options are accessible as well.

Outputs are available in an **Export view** listing current state, at-risk districts, exposed counts, and dissemination maps aligned with LRCS EAP procedures.

5. Climate Service LLM-based AUTO Generator

5.1 Introduction and Purposes

Within the I-CISK project, a new interactive application has been developed to lower the barriers for accessing and using climate data services. The **AUTO Climate Service Composer/Toolbox** is powered by a **Large Language Model (LLM) agent**, which enables users to interact with complex climate data infrastructures through natural language queries.

The purpose of this tool is to **simplify and democratize the creation of tailored climate services**, making them accessible to non-specialist users as well as to experts who require flexible and rapid prototyping capabilities. Instead of writing code or configuring technical workflows, users can simply formulate requests in natural language. The LLM agent interprets these requests, automatically generates the necessary **Jupyter-based code for data processing and visualization**, and guides the user step by step in the analysis.

The system is embedded within a **Streamlit web interface** that provides an intuitive and user-friendly environment. By combining natural language interaction with a **human-in-the-loop approach**, the tool ensures both automation and transparency: the user can inspect, refine, and adapt the generated workflows, maintaining full control over the analysis process.

In practice, the AUTO CS Composer/Toolbox supports users in:

- **Collecting** climate and environmental data from upstream services (e.g., Copernicus CDS, GEOSS) and local datasets.
- **Processing** the data through pre-defined methods such as cleaning, bias correction, or downscaling.
- **Visualizing** the results using tailored indicators, plots, and maps relevant to the user's context.
- **Deploying** outputs either in a web-based dashboard or as reproducible Jupyter notebooks.

By leveraging LLM technology, this tool represents a **paradigm shift** in how climate services can be composed, moving from static, expert-driven workflows to **dynamic, user-driven services** that adapt to the needs of Living Labs and real-world applications. Its ultimate purpose is to enable a more participatory, transparent, and efficient way of transforming climate data into actionable knowledge.

In this deliverable, we first provide a **technical description of the AUTO Climate Service Composer/Toolbox**, including its architecture, IT specifications, and integration within the I-CISK platform; in the second part, we present the **user manual and tutorials**, which illustrate the functionalities of the toolbox through practical, end-user-oriented examples and real use cases from the Living Labs.

5.2 Technical Manual

Introduction

A new interactive application has been developed for the I-Cisk project, based on an LLM agent that allows users to request the collection, processing, and visualization of climate data using natural language. The agent, integrated into a Streamlit web interface, generates custom Jupyter code for data analysis and supports guided interaction with *human-in-the-loop* approach.

Objectives

- Enable natural language queries on climate data via LLM Agent
- Automate the generation of Jupyter code for collection and visualization.
- Provide guided and verifiable interaction (human-in-the-loop).
- Extend the application to any geographic area and variable.

Technologies

The application consists of three main components, each with a specific role within the system architecture:

AI Agent

- **Framework:** Based on [LangGraph](#), a framework for building conversational agents structured as flow graphs, with support for control and memory.
- **LLM Model:** Uses OpenAI's [gpt-4o-mini](#) for natural language processing, understanding of requests, and dynamic selection of features*(tools*) to activate.
- **Main functions:**
 - Parsing of user requests.
 - Activation and orchestration of specific functions (e.g., data collection, code generation).
 - Creation of custom output in text format and Jupyter Notebook.

Web Application

- **Framework:** Implemented with [Streamlit](#), enables rapid prototyping and deployment of interactive interfaces.
- **Interface:**
 - Chat-like mode for user-agent communication.
 - Progressive display of responses and processing steps.
 - Direct access to generated notebooks.
- **Process management:**
 - The entire flow is driven by natural language interactions.
 - Each operation is verifiable and editable by the user in real time.

Dataset / Storage Support

- **Database:** MongoDB.
- **Structure:**
 - User tracking (anonymous or authenticated).
 - Persistence of conversations with the agent.
 - Storage of results and generated files.

Complete structure

Figure 5.2-1: Component diagram of the auto composer structure.

LangGraph zoom-in

LangGraph is an open-source framework designed for **creating LLM-oriented conversational agents** structured as **directional graphs**. It integrates with LangChain and enables **controllable execution flows** that combine the capabilities of language models with flexible and transparent orchestration logic. It is particularly suitable for implementing **modular** and **tool-based agents**, where interaction is not only sequential but also decision-making.

Graph architecture

LangGraph is based on an oriented graph structure in which each node represents a functional unit (e.g., input parsing, LLM activation, tool selection, code writing, etc.), while arcs define the transition logic between states. The management of interactions and internal transitions is governed by an object called State, which represents the current state of the graph and includes:

- Dialogue history (messages),
- The result of previous executions,
- The parameters relevant to the tools,
- The internal state of the flow control.

Each node can read and modify the State, and determine, based on the updated content, which node to activate next.

Graph Navigation and Tool Activation.

During a session, the agent moves through the graph according to dynamically defined **transition rules**. The central node is often an **LLM node**, which is a module that invokes a language model (e.g., **gpt-4o-mini**) to interpret the user's request. The model evaluates the context (dialog + state) and decides:

- Whether to return a direct response,
- Whether to trigger a specific **tool** to perform an action (e.g., generate a notebook),
- Which parameters to pass to the tool,
- Whether further interaction with the user is needed for clarification.

Activation of a tool is done through **function nodes**, which process the input and update the **state** with the result (e.g., path of the generated file). The graph can then return to the LLM node to communicate the result to the user or continue with other steps.

Design advantages:

- **Modularity:** each step is isolated and independently modifiable.
- **Control:** the developer can define conditional transitions and loops.
- **State persistence:** the system keeps track of the conversational context and results generated.
- **Extensibility:** it is easy to add new tools or routing logic within the graph.

Agent Graph Structure

The agent graph is organized around a **central node called the Chatbot**, which is responsible for the overall orchestration of requests and conversational interaction with the user.

Several arcs (edges) branch off from the **Chatbot** node, leading to the activation of various *tools* (*tools*) depending on the nature of the request. The management of each tool is encapsulated in a **dedicated subgraph**, which represents the entire operational flow required to complete the automatic execution of the request.

There are three main functional subgraphs:

- Subgraph for retrieving data from CDS
- Subgraph for the calculation of the SPI Index
- Subgraph for generating code within notebooks.

Figure 5.2-2: Sketch of the auto composer functional subgraphs.

Each subgraph independently and consistently manages the **life cycle of the corresponding tool** through a structure designed to include **pre- and post-execution user interaction phases**, in line with the human-in-the-loop paradigm.

The validation and control logic of this process is documented in detail in the **Human-In-The-Loop** chapter.

Functionalities

Agent tools

Agent tools are functional components of the LLM agent used to perform specific operations in response to user requests. Each tool is responsible for generating a custom Jupyter Notebook, which interacts with the I-Cisk project's pygeoapi API to access climate data and-if required-perform processing or visualization.

Tools are automatically selected by the agent based on the content of the natural language request. Along with tool selection, the agent also extracts from the request the values to be assigned to the input parameters for tool execution, values on which a validity check is then performed and which can then be confirmed or modified before actual execution.

CDS Historic Notebook Tool

Generates a Jupyter Notebook for ingesting historical climate data from CDS datasets. Used CDS datasets are:

- `reanalysis-era5-land-monthly-means` (monthly averages).
- `reanalysis-era5-land` (hourly data).

Parameter	Type	Description
<code>historic_dataset</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>historic_variables</code>	<code>list[str]</code>	None
<code>area</code>	<code>str</code>	<code>list[float]</code>
<code>start_time</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>end_time</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>zarr_output</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>jupyter_notebook</code>	<code>str</code>	None

CDS Forecast Notebook Tool

Generates a Jupyter Notebook for ingesting forecast data from CDS datasets. Used CDS datasets are:

- `Seasonal-Original-Single-Levels` (seasonal temperatures and precipitation).
- `CEMS Early Warning Data Store` (GloFAS - river discharge forecasting).

Parameter	Type	Description
<code>forecast_variables</code>	<code>list[str]</code>	None
<code>area</code>	<code>str</code>	<code>list[float]</code>
<code>init_time</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>lead_time</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>zarr_output</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>jupyter_notebook</code>	<code>str</code>	None

SPI Historic Notebook Tool

Generates a Jupyter Notebook for calculating the **Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI)** on historical data. Uses the CDS datasets `reanalysis-era5-land-monthly-means` and `reanalysis-era5-land` to obtain precipitation data

Parameter	Type	Description
<code>area</code>	<code>str</code>	<code>list[float]</code>
<code>reference_period</code>	<code>tuple[int, int]</code>	Range of reference years for calculation of SPI. Default: (1981, 2010).
<code>start_time</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>end_time</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>jupyter_notebook</code>	<code>str</code>	None

SPI Forecast Notebook Tool

Generates a Jupyter Notebook for calculating **Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI)** forecast values over a given geographic area. Uses CDS `reanalysis-era5-land-monthly-means` datasets for historical precipitation reference data and `Seasonal-Original-Single-Levels` for forecast precipitation data.

Parameter	Type	Description
<code>area</code>	<code>str</code>	<code>list[float]</code>
<code>reference_period</code>	<code>tuple[int, int]</code>	Range of reference years for SPI calculation. Default: (1981, 2010).
<code>init_time</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>lead_time</code>	<code>str</code>	None
<code>jupyter_notebook</code>	<code>str</code>	None

Notebook Code Editor Tool

This tool allows you to edit an existing Jupyter notebook by adding new code cells to the end of the document. It is intended to be used **subsequent to the generation of a notebook** via one of the data collection tools (historical or forecast), when the user requires additional operations such as processing, specific analysis, or custom visualizations.

The distinguishing feature of this tool is its ability to generate code consistent with the pre-existing content of the notebook: in fact, it exploits the variables, structures and data already defined in the previous sections, ensuring operational and semantic continuity. The generated code is therefore "hangable" and non-invasive, designed to extend the existing workflow without changing its original logic.

Parameter	Type	Description
<code>source</code>	<code>str</code>	Name of the <code>.ipynb</code> file to be modified. Must be given as a simple filename (e.g., <code>notebook-output.ipynb</code>), without a path. The file must be in the database.
<code>request</code>	<code>str</code>	Descriptive text of the desired modification. Indicates the type of processing or visualization to be added (e.g., calculating indicators, creating maps or graphs), so as to guide code generation.

Human-In-The-Loop

Interaction with the system is mainly based on a **conversational mode in natural language**, in which the user expresses requests, intentions and possible corrections or approvals through a chat. This approach is maintained **not only in the initial request phase**, but also in all subsequent phases of management, validation and modification of input parameters and tool-generated outputs.

Modeling in the LangGraph graph

Since LangGraph adopts a **graph architecture of nodes and arcs**, the *human-in-the-loop* model was designed as a **series of interactions embedded in the graph itself**, connected to the functional nodes responsible for tool activation. Specifically, each tool is managed through an **autonomous subgraph**, within which the interactive steps with the user are explicitly embedded.

Types of interaction provided

The system supports several modes of user intervention in the flow:

- Additional inputs explicitly requested by the user.
- Modification of parameters automatically pre-filled by the agent.
- Clarifications by the agent when:
 - the parameters detected are insufficient or invalid;
 - confirmation is needed before running the tool;
 - the output obtained needs validation or improvement.

Tool Parent and Interactive Cycle Management

To standardize tool behaviour, an **abstract tool (ParentTool1)** was defined from which all specific tools inherit. This component implements the complete logic of the execution cycle, including the following steps:

1. **Checking for the presence of the mandatory parameters:** if they are missing, abort and prompt the user.
2. **Validation of parameters:** format and logical consistency checks. In case of error, a correction is requested.
3. **Automatic inference of parameters:** use of predefined rules to complete missing inputs.
4. **Request for final confirmation of input parameters.**
5. **Request for approval of output** or suggestion of changes to improve the final result.

Validation and inference rules are configurable for each individual tool, allowing adaptive and specialized behaviour for each use case, while maintaining a common execution structure.

Natural language management

Human-computer interaction continues to be expressed in natural language.

User requests are dynamically constructed by combining:

- Specific templates for each type of interaction (request, confirmation, modification).
- Text descriptions associated with the tool and the parameters involved.

User responses are interpreted by the system through a semantic context that specifies the type of interaction taking place and the expected meaning of the values.

Figure 5.2-3: Auto composer User responses interpretation.

Advantages of the approach

This modeling **simplifies the construction of new tools**, since the interaction logic is already encapsulated in the **ParentTool**.

Each new tool only needs to provide:

- the parameter definition,
- the validation/inference rules,
- the possibly customized messages.

The result is a **consistent, modular and easily extensible** system in which natural user interaction is dynamically adapted to the specific context, without having to rewrite the management logic.

Limitations and future development

The current implementation has a number of physiological limitations, some related to the **nature of the LLM-based agent**, others to the **degree of maturity of the project**.

Current limitations

- **Tool specialization**
The agent's ability to generalize is limited: to cope with heterogeneous or unanticipated requests, it is often necessary to implement specific, purpose-built **tools** to handle particular data collection, processing, or visualization flows. This reduces the flexibility of the system and requires ongoing maintenance.
- **Lack of native knowledge by the LLM of the I-Cisk API.**
The LLM lacks structured and up-to-date knowledge of the I-Cisk API. Although the interface to these APIs is kept as generic as possible, the agent is unable to automatically adapt to substantial changes in logic or response formats. This necessitates the introduction of new tools or manual updates when changes occur.
- **Quality of code generation**
Although LLMs have achieved good levels of accuracy in Python code generation, performance decays in the presence of **complex data structures**, such as multidimensional data cubes. In the absence of sufficiently detailed context, the model may propose code that is incomplete, semantically incorrect, or inconsistent with the user's intent. The output confirmation function specified for the **Notebook Code Editor** Tool is precisely intended to provide more detail when these situations occur.
- **Limited functional coverage**
The system, at present, supports a **limited number of tools** and data sources. However, the architecture is designed to be extensible: in the future it will be possible to include additional datasets (e.g., regional models, satellite observations, local area networks), and expand analytical capabilities (e.g., clustering, anomaly detection, complex indicators).

Future developments

- **Modular expansion of tools**

Progressive introduction of new tools, each specialized for a particular data type, processing, or geographic domain. New tools will inherit the interactive logic already in place, ensuring consistency in the user experience.

- **Dynamic context driven**

To improve the accuracy of code generation, a **dynamic context construction engine** is expected to be introduced, providing the model with detailed information on: structure of available data, semantics of variables, units of measurement and validity constraints. This will improve consistency between user requests and product code.

- **Integration of an automatic validation engine.**

Preventive verification of generated code by controlled execution and detection of errors or warnings, with automatic suggestions for correction or request for clarification to the user.

- **Internal execution of generated notebooks**

In the future, it could be possible to execute Jupyter notebooks directly within the webapp, in an isolated and controlled environment. This will allow the user to **immediately verify the result of the code produced** by the agent. Integrated with the [Notebook Code Editor Tool](#), this mechanism will strengthen *human-in-the-loop* interaction at the output confirmation stage, allowing for real-time changes and adjustments, and making the system more useful and effective in complex data processing.

5.3 User Manual

Introduction

This manual provides step-by-step instructions to guide users through accessing and using the application effectively. It is structured into clear sections: starting with **Login instructions**, followed by a detailed overview of the **main interface**, and finally **practical usage examples** to help users get started quickly.

Login Page

The login page is the entry point to the I-CISK AI Agent Climate Service Composer. From here, users can securely access the application by providing their **User ID**. This step ensures that only authorized users can interact with the system and access the climate data services. The login interface is designed to be minimal and straightforward, containing a single field for the User ID and a button to proceed.

Login

Follow the steps below to log into the application:

- 1. Locate the User ID field:**
In the center of the page, you will see a text box labeled "**User ID**".
- 2. Enter your User ID:**
 - Type the unique User ID that has been provided to you by the system administrator or project team.
 - The correct format of the User ID will typically be:
`usr-*<some-alphanumeric-code>*`
- 3. Click on the *Login* button:**
Once you have entered your User ID, press the **Login** button to proceed.
- 4. Successful login:**
 - If the credentials are correct, you will be redirected to the **Main Interface** of the application.
 - If the login fails, verify that you have typed the User ID correctly. If the issue persists, refer to section "*Requesting a key*" for assistance.

Note: The system does not use traditional passwords. The User ID itself serves as the secure access key for authentication.

Requesting a User Key

If you do not yet have a User ID or have lost your existing one, you must request access from the project team.

1. On the login page, click the "**contact us**" link displayed below the User ID input field.
2. This will redirect you to a contact form where you can submit your request.

Once your request has been approved, you will receive a valid User ID via email or through another secure communication channel. You can then return to the login page and access the system following the steps in "*Login*" section.

Main Interface Overview

After logging in, you are taken to the **main interface**, which is divided into two key areas:

- Chat Section (central area):**
 The main space where you interact with the AI agent through a chat-like interface. Here, you can send requests, view responses, and access generated outputs such as **Python notebooks** or data visualizations.
- Sidebar (left panel):**
 A control panel to manage your sessions and outputs. It includes quick actions (e.g., starting a new chat), a **file manager** for generated notebooks, and a **documentation link** for reference.

Figure 5.3-1: Screenshot of the Auto composer control panel layout.

This layout provides a clear workflow: interact with the agent in the central area while managing files and tools through the sidebar.

Example prompts

At the top of the chat section, four **example prompts** are available to guide the user. They are divided into two groups, based on the type of task performed by the agent.

- SPI Calculation Tool** — Calculation of the SPI index on historical or forecast data.
- Seasonal Forecast Retrieval Tool** — Retrieval of forecast data for precipitation and temperature.
- GloFAS River Discharge Retrieval Tool** — Retrieval of river flow data.
- Code Generation Tool** — Generation of code for customized analyses or visualizations, including on notebooks uploaded by the user.

Figure 5.3-2: Auto composer Generation of code example.

Prompts 1-2-3: API-based tasks

These prompts generate a **new Python notebook** that retrieves climate data using the appropriate **I-CISK APIs**. The user selects one of the example prompts, specifies the required parameters (e.g., location, time range), and sends the request, then the agent will create a notebook containing the code to query the selected API and includes a **standard initial data processing and visualization**.

Prompt 4: Notebook enhancement

This prompt is used to **modify an existing notebook**, either one previously generated by the agent or uploaded by the user. The user describes the additional analyses or visualizations they want while the agent reads the notebook and **adds the necessary code cells** to fulfil the request, without altering the original content.

Types of Agent Responses

The agent can provide two main types of responses during an interaction:

Standard Response

A direct reply where the agent **immediately executes the request** and returns the result. This usually includes:

- A **text explanation** of what was done.
- A **generated Python notebook** containing the code to query APIs and perform basic data processing or visualization.

Interactive Response (Tool Interrupts)

In some cases, the agent needs to **interact with the user before or after execution** to ensure the request is clear and valid. These interactions, called **tool interrupts**, appear in sequence when required and must be resolved before the process continues. The four possible tool interrupt types are:

1. **Missing Input**
 - Triggered when essential information is not provided (e.g., location, date range).
 - The agent asks the user to supply the missing details.
2. **Invalid Input**
 - Triggered when provided information is not valid.
 - Example: selecting an end date for historical data that is later than today.
3. **Input Confirmation**
 - Before running the request, the agent shows the collected parameters and asks the user to confirm they are correct.

hello can we get precipitation forecast?

Sure! Could you please provide the following details for the precipitation forecast:

1. Area of interest (can be a country name, specific geographic area, or bounding box coordinates).
2. Forecast initialization date (YYYY-MM-DD).
3. Lead time (the end date of the forecast, must be after the initialization date).

If you don't have specific preferences, I can use default values.

ok, i want to get data for paris, next month

Using tool: `cds_forecast_notebook_tool`

Parameter	Value
forecast_variables	['precipitation']
area	Paris
init_time	2025-09-01
lead_time	2025-10-01

Interaction required [`CONFIRM_ARGS`]:

Please confirm if the following arguments are correct for the tool execution, or let me know if you would like to make any updates:

- **Forecast Variables:** Total Precipitation
- **Area:** [2.0, 48.0, 3.0, 49.0]
- **Initialization Time:** 2025-09-01
- **Lead Time:** 2025-10-01
- **Zarr Output:** `icisk-ai_cds-forecast-tp_2025-09-09T13-29-49.zarr`
- **Jupyter Notebook:** `icisk-ai_cds-forecast-tp_2025-09-09T13-29-49.ipynb`

Please confirm or suggest any changes.

it's ok

I have retrieved the precipitation forecast data for Paris. Here are the details:

- **Data Source:** `icisk-ai_cds-forecast-tp_2025-09-09T13-29-49.zarr`
- **Jupyter Notebook:** `icisk-ai_cds-forecast-tp_2025-09-09T13-29-49.ipynb`

You can use these files to analyze the precipitation forecast for next month. Let me know if you need further assistance!

Scrivi un messaggio

Figure 5.3-3: Auto composer input confirmation example.

4. Output Confirmation

- After generating a result, the agent may ask the user to confirm that the output meets expectations before finalizing or saving it.

good, can you add to it the code to get a plot of avg measures in whole area? put value on y axis and time on x

Using tool: `code_editor_tool`

Parameter	Value
source	icisk-ai_cds-forecast-tp_2025-09-09T13-29-49.ipynb
code_request	Add code to plot the average precipitation measures over the entire area with time on the x-axis and values on the y-axis.

Interaction required [`CONFIRM_OUTPUT`]:

Here are the generated outputs for your review:

Notebook File:

- icisk-ai_cds-forecast-tp_2025-09-09T13-29-49.ipynb

Generated Code:

```
# Section "Plot Average Precipitation"

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Calculate average precipitation over the time dimension
average_precipitation = dataset_cds_forecast_tp['tp'].mean(dim=('model', 'lat', 'lon'))

# Plotting
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
plt.plot(average_precipitation['time'], average_precipitation.values, marker='o')
plt.title('Average Precipitation Over Time')
plt.xlabel('Time')
plt.ylabel('Average Total Precipitation (m)')
plt.grid()
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Do you want to confirm this output, or would you like to modify some values?

ok, but add a reference to paris in the plot title. also, use color green for the lineplot

Interaction required [`CONFIRM_OUTPUT`]:

The generated output includes a Jupyter notebook file and a Python code snippet for plotting the average precipitation over time. Here are the details:

- Notebook:** icisk-ai_cds-forecast-tp_2025-09-09T13-29-49.ipynb
- Generated Code:**

```
# Section "Plot average precipitation measures"

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Calculate average precipitation over time
average_precipitation = dataset_cds_forecast_tp['tp'].mean(dim='model')

# Create time array for plotting
time_values = dataset_cds_forecast_tp['time'].values

# Plotting
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 5))
plt.plot(time_values, average_precipitation, color='green', linewidth=2)
plt.title('Average Precipitation over Time in Paris')
plt.xlabel('Time')
plt.ylabel('Average Precipitation (m)')
plt.grid()
plt.xticks(rotation=45)
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Would you like to confirm this output as is, or do you want to modify any values in the code? Please let me know how you would like to proceed.

perfect

I have added the code to plot the average precipitation measures over the entire area in the Jupyter notebook. You can find this code in the notebook icisk-ai_cds-forecast-tp_2025-09-09T13-29-49.ipynb. Just run the cell to visualize the average precipitation over time in Paris. Let me know if you need any more assistance!

Scrivi un messaggio

Figure 5.3-4: Auto composer output confirmation example

This structured flow ensures that the interaction is accurate, validated, and transparent, reducing the risk of errors and improving the overall user experience.

Sidebar (Control panel)

The **sidebar** provides quick access to tools and resources that support the main chat interaction. It helps you **manage sessions, generated files, and documentation** without disrupting the conversation flow in the central area.

Quick Actions

The **Quick Actions** section, located at the top of the sidebar, provides essential controls to manage your interaction with the agent.

Figure 5.3-5: Auto composer Quick Actions section

New Chat

- **Purpose:** Starts a completely **new conversation** with the agent.
- **When to use:**
 - If the current conversation becomes confusing or stuck.
 - When you want to begin a **fresh request** without any context from previous messages.
- **Effect:** Clears the current chat history and resets the session.

Tool Selection

- **Purpose:** Allows you to **force the use of a specific tool** for the next request.
- **Usage:**
 - Select the desired tool from the dropdown menu.
 - Send your next message — the agent will execute it **exclusively using the chosen tool**.
- **Limitation:**
 - This option is **disabled while a tool interrupt is active**, ensuring that ongoing clarifications are resolved before switching tools.
 - After the forced execution, the setting resets automatically.

These controls help maintain a smooth workflow, offering a quick way to **restart the chat** or **direct the agent's behaviour** when needed.

File Manager

The **File Manager** allows you to manage all notebooks generated or used within the application.

Figure 5.3-6: Auto composer File Manager section

It provides three main actions:

- **Upload Notebook**
Add an external notebook to the system so the agent can **read and enhance it** with new analyses or visualizations.
- **Preview Notebook**
Open a notebook directly in the browser to **inspect its content** without downloading it.

Figure 5.3-7:- Auto composer Preview Notebook section.

- **Download Notebook**

Save a generated or updated notebook locally for **offline use or further editing**.

This feature centralizes all files in one place, making it easy to track outputs and seamlessly integrate your own notebooks into the workflow.

Documentation

The **Documentation** section provides quick access to external resources:

- **Technical documentation** explaining the system's architecture, APIs, and underlying technologies.
- This **user manual**, offering step-by-step guidance on how to use the application effectively.

Figure 5.3-8: Auto composer access to technical documentation

It serves as a reference point for both technical insights and practical usage instructions.

Limitations

While the application provides a powerful way to interact with climate data through a conversational interface, there are some **important limitations** users should be aware of. Understanding these will help prevent errors and ensure a smoother experience.

Chat Session Stability

If the **chat session encounters an error** or the agent stops responding, the current conversation is considered **compromised**. In these cases, the safest approach is to **start a new chat** using the *New Chat* button in the sidebar. Continuing to work in a broken session may lead to inconsistent outputs or repeated failures.

No Persistent Memory

The system does **not retain past conversations** once they are closed.

- When a chat is ended or the browser session is refreshed, **all previous messages and results are lost**.
- It is recommended to **download generated notebooks** and save important outputs before leaving the application.

Notebook Execution

Notebooks generated by the agent **cannot be executed directly inside the application**. To run and work with them, you must:

1. **Download the notebook** from the File Manager.
2. Execute it in a local Python environment or use a cloud-based service like **Google Colab**.
3. If needed, **re-upload the updated notebook** to the app for further enhancement by the agent.

Other Considerations

- **Tool interrupts must be resolved sequentially:** you cannot switch tools or issue unrelated commands until the current clarification process is complete.
- The proof-of-concept nature of the app means **occasional bugs or unexpected behaviour** may occur, especially when using complex or ambiguous requests.

By keeping these limitations in mind, users can better manage their sessions, avoid losing work, and ensure they are making the most of the available features.

6. Summary

The co-developed Climate Services (CSs) within I-CISK address the information needs of diverse stakeholder groups. Data that traditionally required technical expertise to access and interpret has been **released from silos and meaningfully combined** within the platform. Through the automation of analysis, downscaling, and the integration of local data and knowledge, the CS platform ensures that no advanced modelling expertise is required to align the information with the users' scope of action. As a result, the co-developed CSs enhance the information available to stakeholders, facilitating **better informed decision-making processes**.

The CSs are currently developed as **pre-operational prototypes**, and further refinements will be necessary before large-scale production adoption. Future improvements include the integration of additional datasets and longer time series, enhanced performance and stability, and targeted user interface customizations (e.g., optimized colour schemes).

A key innovation supporting this process is the **AUTO Climate Service Composer/Toolbox**, which provides an LLM-based interactive environment for composing and deploying customized CSs. By enabling users to request data collection, processing, and visualization in natural language, the AUTO Composer lowers technical barriers and supports transparent, human-in-the-loop workflows. This novel functionality not only streamlines the co-development of CSs but also ensures their adaptability to evolving user needs.

The development of the CS platform has utilised a component concept with modular building blocks in order to individually adapt the application to the user needs. The services are in its majority **centrally hosted** utilising shared resources to maximize efficiency. The deployment utilizes GitHub actions and predefined **build pipelines** supporting the rapid and iterative development sprints with a **strong user engagement**. The modular design will allow **re-use of tailored solutions** beyond the I-CISK project without the need to deploy and maintain the entire CS platform.

Overall, a common insight gained through the co-development process is that **anchoring forecasts in historical data and past events**, and relating them to similar anticipated situations, enhances the understanding of climate risks and their impacts. This approach fosters more meaningful engagement with the consequences of a changing climate and strengthens the capacity of stakeholders to plan and respond effectively.

7. Challenges and Solutions

The implementation of the I-CISK platform across diverse Living Labs has provided valuable lessons on the complexities of co-designing climate services. Throughout the development phases, several recurring practical and technical challenges emerged, together with effective solutions adopted by the consortium to ensure successful outcomes. For completeness, the list of challenges and solutions is adopted from previous deliverables and merely refined and expanded here.

- **CHALLENGE:** Discussion with LL hosts and stakeholders are very valuable but need time. This amount of time has been underestimated in the project design.

SOLUTION: Implementation of CSTF boosting productivity. (Later) adapt the focus based on needs of the LL to provide the most valuable and exploitable CS, which might slightly deviate from what has been envisioned in the proposal phase.

- **CHALLENGE:** Availability of external data sources was throughout the project of varying quality (access and data quality wise).

SOLUTION: incorporate data quality checks and (temporarily) store data in the own infrastructure opposed to purely access it through public APIs

- **CHALLENGE:** delay of provision of (local) data

SOLUTION: using synthetic data, but this requires additional work when (i) discussing results with users explaining the source/nature of the data and (ii) replacing the synthetic data with real data when it becomes available.

- **CHALLENGE:** Keeping track of details and mid/long-term decisions and discussions with many people in different constellations.

SOLUTION: We found that a shared online office document (in our case google slides) was a good medium for keeping track of the current state as well as a place for discussions because it allows for text and images to be shared along with a commentary function.

- **CHALLENGE:** While the project and resources come to an end, each LL still has several new ideas and sees refinement opportunities. While this underpins the engagement in the co-design, it also poses a challenge.

SOLUTION: Over the period starting PM 37, this limitation has been made clear by WP5 and the CSTF have jointly (re)prioritised features and refinements of the CS. Further ideas and requests are kept in a back-log of the respective repositories and could directly be addressed in desired further development.

8. Conclusion and Future Work

The I-CISK project has successfully designed, developed, and deployed a **robust, scalable, and modular climate service platform** that delivers actionable climate insights to a diverse set of stakeholders across multiple regions and Living Labs. A key achievement has been the **seamless integration of heterogeneous datasets**—ranging from global sources such as Copernicus ERA5 and GLOFAS, to regional forecasts provided by SMHI, and detailed local monitoring data collected from regional authorities and institutions.

The platform is built on a **cloud-based architecture hosted on the Open Telekom Cloud**, leveraging containerization and orchestration tools such as **Docker and Kubernetes**. This infrastructure ensures reliable performance at scale, while providing flexibility and efficiency in handling large and diverse climate datasets.

At the core of this technical ecosystem lies a **modular back-end framework**. The **Climate Data Ingestor Docker** automates the retrieval, preprocessing, and standardization of datasets, ensuring consistent and reliable data flows. This is coupled with **centralized S3-compatible cloud storage** for optimized data handling, and the **Pygeoapi backend service**, which provides OGC-compliant APIs for standardized access and processing. Together, these components form a powerful and reusable architecture that can be transferred and scaled well beyond the scope of the current project.

A major innovation of I-CISK is the development of the **AUTO Climate Service Composer/Toolbox**. This interactive, LLM-powered application democratizes climate service creation by enabling users to request data collection, processing, and visualization through **natural language interaction** within a user-friendly Streamlit interface. By generating and refining reproducible Jupyter-based workflows in a **human-in-the-loop** fashion, the AUTO Composer significantly lowers technical barriers and supports the participatory co-creation of tailored climate services.

Alongside these back-end and middleware components, strong emphasis has been placed on **stakeholder-driven front-end solutions**. Through iterative co-design with the Living Labs, intuitive graphical interfaces have been developed to accommodate users with different technical backgrounds. Advanced visualization libraries such as **ReactJS, OpenLayers, Highcharts, Leaflet, and Plotly** enhance interpretability and accessibility of complex climate forecasts. Multilingual support, comprehensive documentation, and systematic testing have further reinforced user-friendliness and inclusiveness.

Each Living Lab deployment showcases the **adaptability and modularity** of the I-CISK platform, with tailored solutions aligned to specific local contexts and user needs. These customizations confirm the system's readiness for further **regional and thematic scalability**.

Exploitation pathways and sustainability strategies are outlined in complementary WP5 deliverables, providing clear guidance for the **lasting adoption, expansion, and impact** of the innovations achieved by the I-CISK project.

9. Appendices

9.1 Acronyms

API – Application Programming Interface
CDD – Cooling Degree Days
CDS – Climate Data Store
CDSE – Copernicus Data Space Environment
CIS – Climate Information Services
CNN – Convolutional Neural Network
CSTF – Climate Service Task Forces
DBS – Distribution-Based Scaling
DJF – December, January, February
ENS – Ensemble
ERA5 – ECMWF Reanalysis version 5
ESGF – Earth System Grid Federation
FTP – File Transfer Protocol
GEOSS – Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GLOFAS – Global Flood Awareness System
GUI – Graphical User Interface
IBF – Impact-Based Forecasting
I-CISK – Innovative Climate Information Services for Knowledge
IDW – Inverse Distance Weighting
JSON – JavaScript Object Notation
LL – Living Lab
MAE – Mean Absolute Error
MidAS – Multi-scale bias Adjustment
NetCDF – Network Common Data Form
OGC – Open Geospatial Consortium
OTC – Open Telekom Cloud
POI – Point of Interest
RMSE – Root Mean Squared Error
S3 – Simple Storage Service
SMHI – Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute
SPI – Standard Precipitation Index
SPI-3 – Standardized Precipitation Index (3-month interval)
STAC – SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TCI – Tourism Climatic Index
UHI – Urban Heat Island
WP – Work Package
ZARR – Format for chunked, compressed, N-dimensional arrays

I-CISK

HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

Colophon:

This report has been prepared by the H2020 Research Project “Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge (I-CISK)”. This research project is a part of the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Framework Programme call, “Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal (H2020-LC-GD-2020)”, and has been developed in response to the call topic “Developing end-user products and services for all stakeholders and citizens supporting climate adaptation and mitigation (LC-GD-9-2-2020)”. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037293.

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